

Applying STACK to Pure Maths and Advanced Courses

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Abstract:

STACK is well known for its flexibility in allowing students to enter numeric and algebraic solutions to problems. As such it has been widely adopted in introductory university mathematics courses, and applied mathematics. However, the flexibility of STACK allows it to be successfully used for questions in areas of Pure Mathematics and more advanced topics, including in areas such as proofs, where it has currently seen less use.

This paper will outline creative approaches to writing such STACK questions which maximise the pedagogical benefit to students. The Durham University Department of Mathematical Sciences will be presented as a case study. An introduction to the use of STACK at the Department will be presented, followed by a case study of the successful implementation of automated e-assessment in a first year Discrete Mathematics module, and a discussion of plans to introduce automated e-assessment to the first year Analysis module and more advanced courses for students in later years.

The paper will outline how a collaborative approach to writing such questions can be beneficial, and in particular in situations where course lecturers are less familiar with STACK than other colleagues.

Keywords: collaboration; proof; discrete; analysis

1 Introduction to Mathematical Sciences at Durham

Mathematical Sciences at Durham University is a large department, with an annual intake of around 300 undergraduates. Modules within the Department are also taken by students on the joint honours Natural Sciences degree, and the department further provides introductory mathematics services courses to other departments with its Faculty. Some of the largest Mathematical Sciences modules therefore have in excess of 500 students.

Each of the first year modules has weekly homework assignments, which all students are required to complete. Traditionally this has resulted in a very heavy marking load for staff.

The Department has therefore investigated a number of options for alternatives to homework assignments being marked on paper. Blackboard, the virtual learning environment used by Durham University, offers limited automated e-assessment options (such as multiple choice questions), which are often not suitable for the advanced mathematical techniques being taught. The Department has introduced the Gradescope software for all written homework.

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This allows students to submit scans or photographs of their homework electronically, which can then be marked by staff on a web interface. This enables the use of keyboard shortcuts and quick re-use of the same feedback text for multiple students. This provides significant efficiency savings, but still requires a heavy staff load.

In the 2019-2020 academic year, the department ran a trial of introducing more advanced automated e-assessment, initially using both the Numbas and STACK systems. This proved a significant success, in particular with the more flexible STACK system. Over the years the Department has introduced automated e-assessment into the majority of first year courses, and some second year courses, with half of the assessments in the affected modules being switched to e-assessment quizzes using STACK or Numbas questions, with the remaining assessments remaining manually marked on Gradescope. The change has been well received by staff and students, and has led to the Department to investigate further use of STACK.

2 Analysis of the use of STACK at Durham

The advantages of the ability of automated e-assessment, and in particular STACK, to implement complex mark schemes and provide instant tailored feedback has been well described [Sa13], as has its successful implementation at other universities [ST21].

It is appropriate to analyse the impact the use of STACK in Mathematical Sciences at Durham by using the four lenses proposed by Brookfield for the critical analysis of teaching [Br]: the personal experiences of the author, the experience of other staff within the department, the experience of students, and a look at the literature.

The heavy staff marking load at Durham before the introduction of automated e-assessment had several negative effects. Most directly evident to staff was time that this took away from other tasks, including direct contact time with students, and preparation time for teaching.

More directly evident to students was the effect on the quality of feedback. As discussed extensively in literature [Sh07], feedback on student assessment is very important, particularly in formative assessments, and needs to be received sufficiently soon after the assessment to be full use. However, with all assessment being marked by hand, the very earliest that marks and feedback could be returned to students was a week after the submission deadline. Even with this timescale, markers' workload often meant that they were not able to give students feedback at the level of detail that they wished and the students required. Giving markers more time to produce more detailed feedback would increase the time it took for students to receive this feedback. Splitting the marking of a single assignment between multiple markers could often lead to inconsistent feedback.

The introduction of automated e-assessment using STACK has helped to resolve these issues. Feedback is automatic and the use of advanced potential response trees can ensure that this feedback is detailed and specific to the students' particular submission. Furthermore, the use of randomisation within questions has effectively expanded the size of the question

bank, giving students more resources for revision. Informal consultation with students has revealed that they generally supportive of automated e-assessment, with only a small minority preferring traditional written assessment for all homework assignments.

Many module lecturers have decided to familiarise themselves with STACK to enable them to set their own automated e-assessment. However, a core group of experienced STACK professionals within the Department has allowed the introduction of STACK questions even in cases where lecturers are unfamiliar with the system. A lecturer wishing to introduce e-assessment in their course is paired up with a member of this STACK group and provides them with a list of written homework questions. The two work together to identify which of these questions are suitable to be adapted into STACK. The STACK expert then proceeds to create the STACK versions of the questions, which are then reviewed by the lecturer until the two agree on a final approved version.

This process has seen a lot of success in applied mathematics modules in earlier years of the degree, and more generally in modules where students are expected to produce algebraic answers [Ma21]. However, the success in these areas has prompted an exploration of using STACK in a wider range of modules.

3 Discrete Mathematics as a Case Study

Discrete Mathematics is a first year undergraduate course, focusing primarily on introductory aspects of combinatorics. This was a relatively early module to adapt some of its homework assessments into STACK quizzes, using the original method described above, with the course lecturer working with one member of the STACK group to write the questions.

About half of the original written homework questions involved proofs, and there was significant discussion about how to approach this. While there are ways to implement proof based questions in automated e-assessment (for example filling in blanks), the lecturer ultimately judged that it was important for him to mark proofs that were written out by students in full. The format of question itself had pedagogical importance. Two different formats of a question may test and teach the same material – but one may teach processes better. The judgment on this is often subjective.

Therefore, only questions requiring numerical answers, such as shown in Fig. 1, were used in STACK quizzes. Close discussion with the lecturer allowed the question writer to identify key places in where randomisation of question content, partial credit and personalised feedback could be introduced – making the best use of STACK’s features and providing the best experience for the students.

The order of the questions in the homework assessments had to be changed so that proof based questions were grouped together in the written Gradescope assessments. However, this still provided a good compromise, getting the benefits of STACK on as many questions as possible, while allowing students to practice writing out proofs in full.

Find the number of 6 letter words using the letters V, W, X, Y, Z in which X, Y and Z each occurs at least once.

Your last answer was interpreted as follows:

12194

Check

Hints:

🟡 Your answer is partially correct.

Your answer is close to correct, however, in your inclusion-exclusion calculation you seem to have only considered the number of ways in which one of the letters X, Y, Z and be absent; and also only considered the number of ways in which only one pair of these letters can be absent.

Marks for this submission: 0.50/1.00.

Find the number of 6 letter words using the letters U, V, W, X, Y, Z in which X, Y and Z each occurs at least once.

Your last answer was interpreted as follows:

106548

Check

Hints:

❌ Incorrect answer.

You are approaching the correct answer, but you have made a number of errors in your calculation. Check that you got all of the signs and coefficients correct at all stages in your calculation. Remember that

$$|A \cup B \cup C| = |A| + |B| + |C| - |A \cap B| - |A \cap C| - |B \cap C| + |A \cap B \cap C|.$$

Marks for this submission: 0.00/1.00.

Fig. 1: Implementation of a discrete mathematics question in STACK, showing implementation of partial credit, personalised feedback, and randomisation.

4 Analysis I as a Case Study

Analysis I is another first year module, with an even heavier focus on proof. This means that manual marking for this module can be particularly time consuming but implementation of STACK questions using the method proposed for other modules is difficult.

The Department has therefore decided to experiment with a new, more collaborative procedure, with the same desired outcome of converting half of the module's homework assessments to automated e-assessment quizzes. The core of this new approach is a large working group consisting of both experts in the course, and experts in STACK (with some members falling into both categories).

The existing written questions and provided to and reviewed by the entire team. Meetings are held in which the entire team can discuss which questions are appropriate for automated e-assessment. Having a larger group of people allows for more complete discussion, with the STACK experts being able to communicate more fully the capabilities of STACK, and the module experts being able to more fully communicate the teaching and learning requirements of the module. This has allowed for the group to identify certain proof questions where STACK might be appropriate, and to generate ideas for other e-assessment question types which may be used (for example, re-arranging individual pre-written sentences so that they form a coherent proof).

Once questions suitable for conversion to e-assessment are identified, they can be claimed by individual members of the group, who will do the actual conversion. These questions can then be put together into quizzes, which will sit alongside the remaining written, manually marked assessments. This process is outlined in Fig. 2. This process is currently ongoing, but good current progress in identifying questions suitable for automated e-assessment. As Analysis I is more similar to many modules in later years than many other first year modules, there is a hope that this approach will be suitable for implementing automated e-assessment in these areas.

Fig. 2: Flowchart representing advanced question authoring process

5 Conclusions and Outlook

STACK, and automated e-assessment more generally, has proved a useful and popular tool at the Department of Mathematical Sciences at Durham University. It has allowed students to receive fast and detailed feedback on their homework and freed up staff to devote more time to student contact hours and teaching preparation. The use of a hybrid approach where half of assessments remain written and manually marked has ensured that students can still be tested on their effectiveness with writing longer form answers.

Some questions are not suitable for automated e-assessment, and the judgement on when this is the case can often be subjective. However, collaborative working between module lecturers and STACK experts has proved successful at identifying the best questions for e-assessment and making sure that they are as well designed as possible.

While current roll-out has been limited to primarily to applied mathematics modules, the success with Discrete Mathematics shows that wider implementation is possible. The new, more collaborative method being trialed with the Analysis I module provides a roadmap for the implementation of STACK, and automated e-assessment more generally, to more advanced modules.

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